

DEVELOPING HPC SERVICES

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

In EuroCC* phase 1, Greek National Competence Center (NCC) (EuroCC@Greece)^ has created an ecosystem of tools platforms, training material and databases. In EuroCC Phase 2, a series of planned steps have been taken to harmonize the different products of EuroCC Phase 1 and at the same time to update the EuroCC@Greece key message and future HPC services. The latter consist of utilizing the expertise of the 5 consortium members, the needs of the Greek HPC landscape and the types of users (e.g. Academia, Industry, Public Sector and HPC experts) towards the design of the EuroCC@Greece HPC Services and Service Packs.

* <https://www.eurocc-access.eu>

^ <https://eurocc-greece.gr/>

INTRODUCTION

The mission of EuroCC Phase 2 is to continue the establishment of a network of National Centres of Competence (NCC) in the most efficient way, while continuing to address the differences in the maturity of HPC deployment in Europe, for which improvement has already been noted. In case of Greek National Competence Centre (NCC), represented by the consortium of EuroCC@Greece, EuroCC Phase 2 will continue and extend the activities which were established during the first phase of the EuroCC project. The emphasis will be given on the collaboration with Industry, SMEs and Public Administration. The specific objectives are to:

- I. advance competitiveness in research,
- II. improve effectiveness of government services
- III. promote innovation in industry

Towards accomplishing the goals of EuroCC@Greece and build on what was created in EuroCC 1, the five consortium members, design the new key message, harmonize and complete the EuroCC@Greece ecosystem of tools, platforms, databases and training material, and design a series of HPC Services and Service Packs tailored to Greek HPC needs landscape.

The current paper, present the key aspects of the development of the EuroCC@Greece HPC Services, as it is planned for EuroCC 2 lifetime (2023-2026) and beyond. Our key message is:

Greece's HPC Competence Center

***“Enhancing innovation capacity in Business, Industry and Science
by utilizing advanced High Performance Computing services “***

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GREEK MAPPING OF HPC NEEDS

HPC constitutes a strategic resource in the digital decade dominated by an increasing number of data-intensive applications and services and an ever increasing need to address challenges for the benefit of citizens, businesses, researchers and public administrations around the world. Thus, increasing the usability of HPC, and bridging the gap in HPC, High Performance Data Analytics (HPDA) and Artificial Intelligence (AI), aligned with the needs of the relevant stakeholders is of key importance for Europe and the aim of the Euro CC project.

EuroCC@Greece aiming to create knowledge, skills and providing support for the Greek ecosystem of users, conducted a survey aiming to provide information about the Greek HPC landscape* in academia, industry and public sector during 2021.

The results of the HPC Needs Analysis in Greece revealed that HPC services in Greece are used mostly by academia especially by Postgraduate students and University professors of all levels. On the other hand, the diffusion of HPC in industry and Public Sector in Greece, appears to be quite low in terms of familiarity and HPC services usage.

* Karozis, S., Ziouvelou, X., & Karkaletsis, V. (2023). Mapping the national HPC ecosystem and training needs: The Greek paradigm. *The Journal of Supercomputing*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11227-023-05080-y>

Type of Learner	Not Interested	Type of HPC User (including HPDA/AI)					
		Informational User (Pre-HPC User)	HPC User (Application HPC User)	HPC Developer (Application HPC Developer)	HPC Administrator (System HPC Administrator)	HPC Expert	
		Skill Level 1: Introductory	Skill Level 2: Beginner	Skill Level 3: Intermediate	Skill Level 4: Advanced	Skill Level 5: Highly Advanced	
Student, Academia, Research (BSc, MSc, PhD, post-doc, Professort)	19%	12%	18%	25%	14%	11%	
Industry	Industrial Researcher (Data Scientists)	14%	31%	0%	7%	17%	31%
	Other	15%	19%	32%	16%	19%	0%
Public Sector	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	

WHAT AND FOR WHOM

As such, an HPC Service ecosystem (HPC4U) was designed and build as a blueprint to be materialized during EuroCC Phase 2. **HPC4U** aims to accommodate users from Academia, Industry, Public Sector and HPC experts to find out how they can accelerate their research and development, by utilizing tools, methods and infrastructure from HPC, Big Data and AI fields.

“EuroCC@Greece the HPC-way to Science 2.0 and Industry 4.0”

Potential users can follow a series of steps, to self-assess their HPC needs and find the HPC4U services (see page 4) that meet their needs. In addition, information for EuroCC@Greece consultation team to be prepared, is asked as a description of the case that potential can utilize the HPC4U services and be accelerated. The outcome of the workflow is to enable the consultation team to build a customized HPC4U service pack (see page 5).

SIX HPC SERVICES

EuroCC@Greece HPC Services were defined based on four key elements:

1. The Greek HPC needs analysis
2. The types of HPC users
3. The expertise of EuroCC@Greece consortium
4. The tools that EuroCC offers as a project

The table below, presents the services designed and planned to be offered by EuroCC@Greece.

HPC4U services	Description	Status
Code4HPC	<i>High-level support in optimizing HPC, ML, and AI code development for enhanced performance and scalability</i>	
Train4HPC	<i>The training service is comprised of four different products to fit the needs of all HPC Greek users.</i> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. <i>Perform a training academy events online or physical, customized for Academia, Industry, Public Sector, Familiarity level and Sector.</i> 2. <i>Offering a standard video tutorial material</i> 3. <i>Offering a Greek Massive Open Online Course (MOOC) with a training certificate</i> 4. <i>Offering HPC Industrial Internships+</i> 	
Access2HPC	<i>Consultation on how to successfully gain access to national or EU HPC infrastructure*</i>	
Experts4HPC	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. <i>Providing visibility to HPC experts via the Greek HPC experts registry[^]</i> 2. <i>Providing access to a registry of Greek HPC Experts[^] to accommodate the need of academia and industry to be linked with an expert.</i> 	
Ready4HPC	<i>SME assessment tool offered by EuroCC centrally</i>	

+ <https://eurocc-greece.gr/industrial-internship/>

* <https://hpc.gmet.gr/en/> <https://eurohpc-ju.europa.eu/news/access-eurohpc-supercomputers-now-open>

[^] <https://hub.eurocc-greece.gr/>

FOUR HPC SERVICE PACKS

As it is mentioned above, the HPC user are coming from Academia, Industry and Public Sector, with the last two, lacking in using HPC services compare to Academia. Based on the categorization, EuroCC@Greece, design 4 HPC4U Service Packs. The Services Packs are working as a group of HPC services that a user from Academia, Industry, Public Sector or an Expert, most possible may need. As such, the HPC4U Service Packs are working as a blueprint to help potential users to choose their HPC Services based on their needs and familiarity. It is used as a starting point for the consultation meeting and discussion between EuroCC@Greece and the potential HPC user, and they can be changed and be completed.

The table below presents the EuroCC@Greece HPC4U Service Packs for each user type accordingly.

HP4U Service Packs	HPC4U Services
HPC4Industry	<i>Ready4HPC Train4HPC Code4HPC Access2HPC</i>
HPC4Academia	<i>Train4HPC Ready4HPC Code4HPC Access2HPC</i>
HPC4PublicSector	<i>Ready4HPC Train4HPC</i>
HPC4Experts	<i>Experts4HPC Train4HPC</i>

CONCLUSIONS

EuroCC@Greece designed and started to build a new HPC services ecosystem (HPC4U) to meet the HPC needs of Greek landscape. The needs were derived based on a HPC needs survey analysis. The HPC4U services were taken into account

1. The Greek HPC needs analysis
2. The types of HPC users
3. The expertise of EuroCC@Greece consortium
4. The tools that EuroCC offers as a project

The HPC4U service tackle the need for optimizing codes for use it in HPC infrastructure, for training in different ways and levels, for finding an HPC expert to assist you, for assessing the HPC readiness of your organisation and for improving the HPC capabilities of your organization.

In addition, to help the potential HPC users, the concept of HP4U Services Packs was designed. The service packs are used a pre-selection of services that may concern the user's needs based on the different types of HPC users (Academia, Industry, Public Sector and Experts).

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ABOUT US

Contact us at

contact@eurocc-greece.gr

A National Competence Center is the reference and single point of contact and coordination on a national level for HPC. Its missions are to analyse, implement and coordinate all necessary activities and offer services to end users to cover their needs: from access to resources and technological consultancy to the provision of training courses for academia, public administrations and industry.

The aim is to bring together the necessary expertise to set up a cross-European network of NCCs in HPC-related topics with 31 participating members and associated states and to provide a broad service portfolio tailored to the respective national needs of academia, public administrations and industry. Each NCC has a presentation page with their skills and contact information.

EuroCC@Greece is one of the 33 HPC Competence Centres, built in the framework of the European High Performance Computing Joint Undertaking (EuroHPC JU).

The overall objective of the Greek National Competence Center is to enable the efficient uptake of HPC technologies with the 3-fold goal to:

1. advance competitiveness in research
2. improve effectiveness of government services and
3. promote innovation in industry.

In order to achieve this goal, the NCC will address the issues of training and skills development, technology transfer, collaboration with Industry, competence mapping and awareness raising, in the fields of High Performance Computing, High Performance Data Analytics, Artificial Intelligence and Big Data.

Consortium

The Greek National Competence Center "EuroCC@Greece", is run by a consortium of 5 institutions, namely

- National Infrastructures for Research and Technology (GRNET)
- National Center for Scientific Research "Demokritos" (NCSR)
- Foundation for Research and Technology – Hellas (FORTH)
- Institute of Communication and Computer Systems of NTUA (ICCS)
- Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (AUTH)

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